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**First record of *Eodorcadion altaicum* (Suvorov, 1909) from
Russia with description of a new subspecies
(Coleoptera: Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract: First record of *Eodorcadion altaicum* (Suvorov, 1909) for Russia is proposed. *E. a. violovitshi* **spp. n.** is described from Altay Republic.

Introduction

Eodorcadion altaicum (Suvorov, 1909) is distributed in East Kazakhstan along Naryn River valley and around upper level of Bukhtarma River.

A discovery of the new population in Russia was quite unexpected. It is described below as a new subspecies.

Results

Eodorcadion altaicum violovitshi **spp. n.**

Fig. 1

Type locality. Altay Republic of Russia, north of Ust-Koksa village, Katun River valley, 50°16'40.3"N, 85°37'39.5"E, 1028 m.

Description. Only two males available; body, legs and antennae uniformly brown, relatively glabrous; frons with rough irregular sculpture, with several small patches of very short fine white setae laterally, central frontal furrow smoothed; vertex glabrous, with very dense, big, irregular punctation; genae and occiput with very fine

white pubescence; prothorax slightly wider anteriorly than posteriorly; basally slightly (holotype) or considerably (paratype) wider than long; antennae slightly shorter than body, glabrous; 1st antennal joint about as long as 3rd and much longer than 4th; pronotum glabrous, with strong irregular sculpture and deep central longitudinal furrow with small smooth shining areas along its length; thoracic lateral spines short, but sharpened, with dense fine white pubescence at bases; scutellum glabrous, smooth and shining, triangular with rounded apex; elytra about 1.6 times longer than wide; moderately convex; without any traces of dorsal carinae; without punctation, but matte, with microsculpture; without any traces of white stripes; humeral carinae obliterated, although barely outlined anteriorly; ventral bodyside and legs with fine dense white pubescence; body length of the holotype: 13.8 mm, body width (at elytral middle): 5.13 mm; body length of the paratype: 14.0 mm, body width (at elytral middle): 5.13 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *E. altaicum violovitshi* **ssp. n.** is not geographically too far from the nominative subspecies. *E. a. altaicum* (Suvorov, 1909) is distributed in Kazakhstan about 100 km southwards along Bukhtarma and Naryn river valleys. The nominative subspecies also has glabrous elytra (without humeral white stripes), but differs by several characters: body much wider (elytra about 1.5 times longer than wide) and usually bigger; average length in males is about 15 mm, but could be up to 17 mm or slightly more; elytra strongly convex, with distinct regular punctation, shining, without misrosculpture between punctures; small, short rudiments of humeral white stripes can be observed near elytral apices.

Material. Holotype, male, Altay Republic of Russia, north of Ust-Koksa village, Katun River valley, 50°16'40.3"N, 85°37'39.5"E, h-1028 m, VII.1965, N.A. Violovitsh leg. - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia); paratype, male with same label - Institute of Human Ecology of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences.

Distribution. A single population is known in Altay Republic of Russia, north of Ust-Koksa village, Katun River valley, 50°16'40.3"N, 85°37'39.5"E, 1028 m.

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to well known Russian entomologist Nikolay Alexandrovitch Violovitsh (1913-1986), who collected the type series.

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Fig. 1. *Eodorcadion altaicum violovitshi* ssp. n. Holotype, male.

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